

IPCC DDC at DKRZ: Annual Report 2023

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1. Summary

The total DDC data volume provided by IPCC DDC hosted at DKRZ has increased from 1.9 PBytes to 2.0 PBytes due to the finalization of the long-term archival of the AR6 datasets. The volume for the AR6 Reference data archive at the end of 2023 was 169 TBytes, where 35 TBytes belong to SR1.5 datasets from the HAPPI project and 134 TBytes to AR6 CMIP6 input datasets. Other shares are 1.6 PBytes in the AR5 Reference Archive, ca. 1 TByte in the AR4 Reference Archive, and ≤ 10 GBytes each in the Reference Archives for FAR, SAR, and TAR.

IPCC DDC users downloaded ca. 140 TBytes and 197 000 datasets in 2023 with mean monthly downloads of 16 000 datasets/month and 12 TBytes/month. The trend of decreasing data downloads have continued, which are caused by the decreasing AR5 data downloads, which dominate the DDC statistics. The share of the data downloads from ESGF portal users remain > 90 %. Data download numbers of previous ARs show increases from 2022 to 2023 between $+23$ % for AR4 and $+87$ % for TAR to $+250$ % for SAR and a decrease of -59 % for AR5. AR6 data downloads in 2023 are four times the 2022 values in number and eight times in volume.

The download counts per continent are less dominated by Asian users than in the previous years. The 39 % download share from Asian users was followed by 33 % from North American users. European users contributed 20 %, African users 8 % and Australian and South American users together less than 1 % to the total download counts in 2023. Nearly half (46 %) of the datasets in 2023 were downloaded from Africa, Asia and South America, which can be roughly regarded as developing and economy-in-transition countries.

DDC users requested no data for selected areas on storage media in 2023. This mailing service will be phased out by DKRZ and replaced by an online download option for regional CMIP6 input data of AR6.

2. Evolution of data access

From mid 2020 to January 2021, massive downloads of a single dataset from a single European ESGF user occurred. These technical downloads were carefully eliminated from the statistics.

The total downloads in 2023, 197 000 datasets or 140 TBytes, are ca. 56 % of the downloads in 2022 (**Figure 1**), which is caused by the decrease in AR5/CMIP5 input dataset downloads by 53 % in volume and number. As CMIP6 input data has been available for several years, the interest of data users shifts from CMIP5 to CMIP6. The DDC's data content is dominated by CMIP5 data with a share of 80 % in number and 90 % in volume of the total DDC content. The mean monthly data downloads are ca. 12 TBytes/month and ca. 16 000 datasets/month.

The monthly downloads decreased from the beginning of 2023 towards mid of the year before increasing to the maximum monthly value of ca. 28 TBytes and 30 000 datasets in October/November 2023.

Compared to the total downloads from DKRZ's long-term archive, the download numbers from the DDC Reference Data Archives contributes ca. 90 % to the total download numbers from DKRZ's long-term archive, while it accounts for only ca. 76 % of the content. The data contained in the DDC are the most popular datasets in DKRZ's long-term archive.

Figure 1: Total data download counts and volumes per months over the last three years in GBytes from the IPCC DDC reference archive.

3. Geographical distribution of data access

For the IPCC DDC AR5 data, direct data access at the DKRZ and access via ESGF are supported. Downloads from ESGF dominate the statistics with > 90 % of the downloads. The ESGF file downloads in 2023 provided by CMCC were merged with the DDC continental download information (**Figure 2**). As no information on the number of active users is available for the dominating ESGF downloads, no reliable information on active users can be provided for 2023.

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Figure 2: Number of dataset downloads (download counts) per continent for 2023.

3.1 Data on storage media

No data subsets for selected regions on storage media were requested by DDC users in 2023. DKRZ will not provide this service for AR6 but plans to provide these data subsets through a download service. Thus, the mailing service of data subsets on storage media will be phased out.

4. Data access by category AR

The monthly download rates in 2023 from the IPCC DDC Reference Data Archive were dominated by AR5 downloads as in the previous years (**Figure 3**; online monthly download statistics¹). The majority of AR5 datasets (> 90 %) were downloaded via DKRZ's DDC ESGF data node. The numbers show a total download volume of ca. 130 TByte for AR5 in 2023, which is ca. 53 % of the download volume of the previous year. The individual 190 000 dataset downloads for AR5 in 2023 are ca. 41 % of the 2022 downloads. Users' interest in CMIP data has been shifting from CMIP5 towards CMIP6 datasets.

¹ Online monthly download statistics are available at:

https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC
https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC_AR6
https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC_AR5
https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC_AR4

Figure 3: Total annual data download counts (left) and volumes in GBytes (right) over the last five years for the different DDC reference archives (without FAR; AR6 includes SR1.5).

Downloads in 2023 for the oldest ARs show increased numbers compared to 2022 ranging between +23 % for AR4 and +87 % for TAR to +250 % for SAR. The corresponding download volumes show increases for SAR and TAR but a -30 % decrease for AR4. The datasets related to AR6 consist of SR1.5 model data from the HAPPI project and the recently long-term archived CMIP6 input datasets and AR6 intermediate datasets. The downloaded volume of AR6-related datasets in 2023 is 8 times the value in 2022 as more datasets became available in the DDC AR6 Reference Data Archive. Because of the relatively low total download volume for AR6 data compared to the dominating AR5 data, this increase can only slightly compensate for the decrease in AR5 data downloads. Thus, the total DDC data downloads have decreased from 2022 to 2023.

5. Review of user queries

User requests are directed to the DDC Partner DKRZ and for AR5 data partly to the ESGF support. A separation of user requests on IPCC DDC issues is not possible. The joint DDC support infrastructure was set up end of 2021. No requests were forwarded to DKRZ from there. DKRZ forwarded a few requests to the DDC Partners.

In parallel to the regular user support channels, additional requests were sent to individuals at the modelling centers or at the data centers.

6. News and activities

About 51 TBytes of AR6 CMIP6 input datasets were archived in the AR6 Reference Data Archive in 2023 in addition to the 83 TBytes archived in 2022. The archival of AR6 data was finalized (**Figure 4**). All AR6 data collections were made available through the joint DDC catalog.

Figure 4: Data long-term archival in the AR6 Reference Data Archive has been finalized during 2023 (top: CMIP6 input datasets, bottom: intermediate datasets).

Apart from the first handover meeting with WGI AR7 TSU, activities in liaison with CMIP and contributions to the targeted use of provenance records in AR7 to collect information from the IPCC authors were carried out:

- CMIP6 data usage analysis:

- CMIP6 data usage in IPCC AR6 has been made accessible as part of the CMIP6 Citation Service at: https://bit.ly/CMIP6_in_IPCC
- CMIP6 variable usage in IPCC AR6 WGI for the CMIP7 baseline variable discussion is provided at:
<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/14YSglype4fFtnXb4DNMmgXxYQILLC0wy>
- Discussions on data and infrastructure requirements from IPCC as TG Data-DDC liaison within CMIP-WIP
- Inquiries and discussions around the AR7 recommendation on usage of provenance records for the CMIP input data archival in the DDC through IPCC's Figure Manager.

Remaining tasks related to the AR6 Reference Data Archive are

- the publication of the AR6 Reference Data Archive through the ESGF portal,
- the provision of selected variables for regions, and
- the joint effort with CEDA to retrofit CMIP6 usage information in AR6 WGI figures.